

DETAILED TUTORIAL

Steps 1 through 5 assume readers are using Sentinel.jl, which is a GPU accelerated library in Julia for programmatically working with European Space Agency Sentinel 2 and 5 data. Julia is a high-performance programming language designed to combine the syntactic benefits of high-level scripted languages, such as Python and R, with the computation performance of statically-typed languages, such as C. It also offers built-in parallel computing capabilities and easy interoperability with other programming languages.

Steps 5 through 8 provide, when possible, alternative examples with the Geospatial Data Abstraction Library (GDAL). GDAL is a reliable tool for many open-source remote sensing applications, such as Q-GIS. The standard library includes a vast range of command-line scripts which are easy to use and extensively documented online.

Readers willing to conduct Steps 1 through 4 should first install the Julia programming language, which is available at <https://julialang.org>. Sentinel.jl can be installed through Julia's built-in package manager. Newer versions are also available on the GitHub repository at <https://github.com/mhudecheck/Sentinel.jl>. Readers are also strongly recommended to use a computer with an Nvidia GPU with at least 8GB of video RAM and a working version of the CUDA library to take advantage of the extensive performance benefits offered by GPU acceleration.

Readers should also install the Geospatial Data Abstraction Library (GDAL), which is available at <https://gdal.org>. Step 10 of this tutorial uses the `exactextract` command line application, which is available at <https://github.com/isciences/exactextract>. Other applications, such as the R raster library, can be used in lieu of `exactextract` to calculate zonal statistics.

Sentinel-2 satellite captures are divided into granules that correspond to 100 km x 100km Military Reference Grid System (MGRS) tiles. Each tile consists of a UTM zone number, a latitude

band letter, and a grid square designation. As a visualized source to find MGRS tile IDs, we recommend the Australian Institute of Marine Science (AIMS) Sentinel-2 UTM Tiling Grid, which can be found by searching <https://eatlas.org.au>.

Not all steps detailed in this tutorial may be accomplished with any given software application. The appropriate software application or library for each step is included in the title of each step. Where applicable, we also provide to outline the general process.

Step 1: Initialize Repository Access and Pull Capture CSV File (Sentinel.jl)

There are several ways to identify and download Sentinel 2 imagery data. The European Space Agency (ESA) releases two types of imagery products, Level-1C top-of-atmosphere, and Level-2A bottom-of-atmosphere reflectances.

Sentinel-2 L1C and L2A products are freely available from the ESA's Copernicus Open Access Hub and the Google Public Cloud Data (GPCD) program. Readers who are working with a region subject to little cloud cover or who are otherwise less technically inclined should consider using the Copernicus Dataspace Browser, which can be found at <https://browser.dataspace.copernicus.eu>. Those who are more technically inclined may programmatically access Sentinel-2 products with either the Open Access Hub or Google Public Cloud Data APIs. The Open Access Hub archives captures after a certain date. For this reason, the remainder of this tutorial assumes that readers are working with the Google Public Cloud Data repository.

The following step assumes that readers have a working Google Account and saved their Google Cloud API validated credentials to their working directory as a .json file. More information, along with instructions on how to do this, can be found at <https://cloud.google.com/docs/>. Readers working with Sentinel.jl should initialize their Google Cloud API credentials by running `cloudInit("credentials.json")`.

Sentinel-2 L1C and L2A product offerings available on GPCD are documented in single, albeit comparatively large, CSV files. These files store a vast amount of metadata for each available product, such as capture times, extents, and access directories. This simplifies the programmatical search and filter of GPCD's product collection, thereby eliminating the need for searching the online directory for each product individually.

Readers working with Sentinel.jl can download these CSV files by running `safeList()`, which retrieves and opens a list of ESA SAFE files from GPCD. More information on `safeList()` is available in the Sentinel.jl help documentation.

Pseudocode

```
initialize Google Cloud API credentials  
download and open CSV
```

Julia

```
myCredentials = "./credentials.json"  
cloudInit(myCredentials)  
captureData = safeList(; level="L1C")
```

Individual SAFE files can be downloaded online at <https://scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus>, which offers an easy-to-use graphical interface.

Step 2: Search for Sentinel-2 Products (Sentinel.jl)

As a next step, readers should search the CSV capture file to identify products for their MGRS tile(s). They may also want to restrict their target list to captures that cover certain date ranges or lower cloud coverage values. This can be done by running `filterList()`.

Because each "swath", or satellite orbit, may not completely cover an MGRS tile extant, readers may need to download a second capture file from the orbit that immediately preceded or followed their original capture file, in order to get full tile coverage. The GPCD metadata for L2A products comes with "no data" information which can be used to estimate whether or not your capture covers your tile. However, readers working with L1C captures may run

safeCoverageData(), which calculates the geometries for each available GPCD product in the dataset, in order to determine whether or not their capture has full coverage.

Pseudocode

for each tile in your available product list:
 filter based on year and cloud cover
 for each row in your filtered list (L1C products only):
 retrieve and store capture geometries

Julia

```
myTargetDataframe = filteredList("captureData", "mgrs_tile", "startDate", "endDate")*  
for i in 1:nrow(myTargetDataframe)  
    noData, geometry = safeCoverageData(myTargetDataframe[i, BASE_URL]  
    myTargetDataframe[i, :noData] = noData  
    myTargetDataframe[i, :geometry] = geometry  
* Note that dates should be created with Date(year, month, day).
```

Step 3: Download Captures (Sentinel.jl | Other)

Readers may now download the Sentinel-2 captures. In Sentinel.jl, this is done by passing a data frame with your target list of captures to checkDownload(). For smaller collections, this may also be done individually by hand by either going to the url provided in the capture data frame in a web browser or by searching for the product by name on <https://scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus>.

Readers likely should restrict the number of downloaded captures to a reasonable amount. A good rule of thumb for granules without any cloud-free captures within a given time frame is to download three to five captures for each 'slice' of the target MGRS tile. For cloudier regions where the satellite swath does not cover the full extent of the tile, readers may need to download up to ten captures in order to create a reasonably cloud free composite.

Pseudocode

identify captures for download
for each tile in target list:
 download satellite imagery for the tile

Julia

```
downloadTiles(myTargetDataframe, nrow(myTargetDataframe); cache = cache)
```

Step 4: Create Cloud Masks (Sentinel.jl)

The cloud masks that are included in the LIC captures are, unfortunately, not accurate enough for regions that experience significant cloud cover and fog. Because of this, readers may want to generate their own cloud cover masks. This can be done by either training an image segmentation model on one of the many publicly available labeled training datasets, or by simply using a pre-trained model.

Note: It's crucial to have a working environment with all required packages and Python dependencies installed. This should be done outside of the Julia working environment.

Once readers have installed all of the requirements for CloudSen12, in Sentinel.jl, they may pass the same target data frame as was used for downloadTiles() to processSAFE() which processes the individual SAFE files, and generates the cloud masks with createScreen(), which is a Julia wrapper for CloudSen12. The cloud masks are then saved to the specified directory.

Pseudocode

for each capture in collection of downloaded captures:

 load capture

 run pre-trained image segmentation model

 save cloud mask as geotiff

Julia

```
processSAFE(myTargetDataframe, "./saveDir/")
```

Step 5: Interpolate (Resize) Raster Bands (Sentinel.jl | GDAL)

Many of the algorithms for land change detection require all input bands to have the same dimensions. Detection accuracy also improves, in many cases, when bands beyond Red, Green, and Blue are included. However, Sentinel-2 raster bands come in either 10m x 10m, 20m x 20m, or 30m x 30m resolutions. If, for instance, readers want to include one of the many infrared bands in their analysis, they will likely first need to homogenize, or interpolate, all of the other selected raster bands to the same dimension.

This process is computationally expensive. Readers working with GDAL or another software application will likely want to allocate at least an hour for each SAFE capture file. However, due to the performance benefits of GPU acceleration, readers working with Sentinel.jl and a working version of the Nvidia CUDA library can interpolate a SAFE capture file in less than a second. Sentinel.jl takes advantage of the parallel processing capabilities of GPUs to efficiently resize large raster datasets. This is crucial in image processing tasks, especially when working with satellite imagery, which can be vast and require consistent dimensions for further processing. In Sentinel.jl, interpolation can be done with `resizeTensors!()`, which takes a SAFE file loaded into the Julia working environment with either `processSAFE()` or `loadGeoTiff()`, passes each raster band in the SAFE file to the GPU, interpolates the raster band with a nearest neighbor algorithm, and overwrites the original loaded raster band with the interpolated version.

For readers who do not have either an Nvidia GPU or who are not working with Sentinel.jl, raster band interpolation can be done with GDAL by running `gdalwarp` or `gdal_translate` in a command terminal.

Pseudocode

```
for each capture in collection of downloaded captures:
  for each band matrix in capture:
    if size of matrix is not (dimSize, dimSize):
      transfer matrix to GPU (if not already on GPU)
      matrix = resize(matrix, dimSize, dimSize; returnGPU=gpu)
      capture[band] = matrix
function resize(matrix, width, height, interpolation, smoothing):
  create a texture array from the band matrix
  determine interpolation type (linear or nearest neighbor)
  create a CUDA texture with the specified interpolation
  allocate memory for the output array on the GPU
  launch the CUDA kernel to resize the input using the texture
  return the resized array
```

Julia

```
resizeTensors!(“loaded collection of SAFE capture files”)
```

GDAL

```
gdalwarp -tr 10 10 -r bilinear /path/.../Bxx.jp2 output_bxx.tif*
```

Note: With GDAL, each band must be interpolated individually. If readers are using `gdalwarp` in particular, they will also need to point the command to the individual JPEG2000 (.jp2) image for that band.

Step 6: Clean Raster Bands and Apply Cloud Masks (Sentinel.jl | GDAL)

This step consists of two parts. Sentinel-2 captures, on occasion, include scan line artifacts that appear most often on swath capture edges. If readers are working with captures where the swath does not cover the entire MGRS tile, they should inspect and, if necessary, remove scan line artifacts before progressing further.

In Sentinel.jl, this can be done by either calling `cleanScanLines!()` on each individual raster band or, more simply, as part of the same function, `applyScreens!()`, that applies the cloud masks to your targeted capture files. The function `cleanScanLines!()` detects and overwrites scan line intersections. The function `applyScreens!()` first calls `cleanScanLines!()`, then applies the cloud mask through element-wise tensor multiplication of each raster band with the corresponding cloud screen. Both functions overwrite the previous raster band loaded into memory. This process, although cumbersome, ensures that subsequent image processing does not consider cloud-covered regions, leading to more accurate results.

GDAL and most other open-source geospatial applications do not come with predefined functions for removing scan line artifacts. It is possible to create a cloud screen with GDAL from Scene Classification (SCL) raster included by the ESA in L1C and L2A capture products. However, readers should be aware that SCL classifications are relatively inaccurate and, in cloudier regions, may lead to poor results.

Pseudocode

```
for each screen in screens:  
  for each band matrix in capture:  
    matrix = transfer matrix to GPU  
    screen = transfer screen to GPU  
    if scanning is required:
```

```
clean scan lines for matrix
screened_band = multiply matrix and screen element-wise
capture[band] = screened_band
```

Julia

```
applyScreens!(“interpolated collection of SAFE capture files”)
```

GDAL

```
gdal_calc.py -A /path/.../SCL.jp2 --outfile=cloud_mask.tif --calc="(A==8) | (A==3)" --
NoDataValue=0
```

```
gdal_calc.py -A /path/.../output_bxx.tif -B cloud_mask.tif --
outfile=masked_output_bxx.tif --calc="A*B" --NoDataValue=0
```

Step 7: Normalize Raster Band Distributions (Sentinel.jl)

Normalization is an essential process in image processing and ensures that the pixel values of raster bands are consistent and comparable. It first calculates the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) for the bands to differentiate between water and ground. Water and ground have very different spectral signatures. For instance, water typically absorbs more in the visible spectrum and reflects more in the near-infrared (NIR) spectrum, while vegetation reflects more in the visible and less in the NIR. Normalizing them separately ensures that their unique spectral characteristics are preserved and not diluted by each other. Then, using these NDWI values, it computes masks for water and ground. Each band is then normalized with respect to water or ground.

In Sentinel.jl, band normalization can be done with `normalizeRasters()`, which takes two raster bands and normalizes their values based on sampling and either linear or k-means normalization. The normalization process also uses trimmed means, which helps reduce the influence of outliers or extreme values. This ensures that the raster bands are on a similar scale, making subsequent analyses more accurate and consistent. Band normalization is also done automatically in `mergeRasters()`, which combines the individual composites into a single cloud free composite. Unfortunately, GDAL and many other open-source geospatial applications do not support raster band normalization.

Pseudocode

See Step 8

Julia

```
normalizeRasters("Capture A Band A", "Capture B Band A")
```

OR

```
mergeRasters("interpolated collection of SAFE capture files")
```

Step 8: Composite Captures into Single Raster (Sentinel.jl | GDAL)

Finally, readers merge each of the raster bands in their collection to form a single composite. There are two common approaches. Readers can use the first masked raster band as a baseline and use each of the subsequent captures to “fill in the blanks”. They may also take the average of each composite mask raster band. The Sentinel.jl function `mergeRasters()` supports both approaches. Although GDAL does not support compositing out of the box, it can be done by first creating a raster stack with `gdal_merge.py`, then computing an averaged raster from the raster stack with `gdal_calc.py`. This process must be repeated for each raster band. Unlike Sentinel.jl, GDAL does not take into account missing values.

Pseudocode (Steps 7 and 8)

```
for each capture in downloaded captures:
  compute NDWI for the first tensor in the collection to get water and ground masks
  for each band in the first tensor:
    normalize the band based on water and ground masks
  for each subsequent tensor in the collection:
    compute its NDWI and get water and ground masks
    normalize its corresponding band based on water and ground masks
  merge the normalized bands
  append the merged band to the result tensor
return the composite tensor
```

Julia

```
mergeRasters("interpolated collection of SAFE capture files")*
```

GDAL

```
gdal_merge.py -separate -o stacked.tif capture1_B03.jp2 capture2_B03.jp2
capture3_B03.jp2 ...
gdal_calc.py -A stacked.tif --A_band=1 -B stacked.tif --B_band=2 -C stacked.tif --
C_band=3 ... --outfile=averaged.tif --calc="(A + B + C + ...) / number_of_captures"
```

If readers are using Sentinel.jl, they should save their cloud free composite with `saveGeoTiff()` before continuing.

Julia

```
saveGeoTiff("cloud free composite", "spatial information", "cloudFreeComposite.tif")*
```

Note: Spatial metadata is returned automatically with either `loadGeoTiff()` or `processSpatial()`.

Step 9: Analysis (Sentinel.jl)

Readers can find a wealth of information online, along with step-by-step tutorials, for unsupervised and supervised approaches to imagery analysis. The analytical approach readers choose will depend entirely on their use case, comfort level with emerging deep learning image segmentation and classification approaches, as well as training data availability.

This step assumes that readers are conducting a simple unsupervised k-means clustering analysis on their cloud free composite. In Julia, this can be done with `Clustering.jl`, which is a CPU-only library for performing cluster analysis.

`Sentinel.jl` saves raster band data as nested array. Each entry includes a two-element array, where the first element is the raster name and the second element is a 10980 x 10980 matrix with the raster band data. In order to convert this into a format usable with the `Clustering.jl` `kmeans()` library, the raster band data first has to be extracted, then converted into a single vector and concatenated with the other raster bands into a single matrix. In our case, because we are working with thirteen raster bands, the matrix inputted into `kmeans()` will be (10980x10980) x 13.

Pseudocode

```
for each cloud free composite "composite" in collection of composites:  
  load composite  
  for each matrix band in composite:  
    convert matrix band to vector  
  concatenate vectors into single matrix
```

```
run kmeans
visualize results
screen for cluster assignments
save results as a geotiff
```

In Julia, this can be accomplished by:

using Clusters

```
raster_data = loadGeoTiff("./path/.../cloudFreeComposite.tif")
band_data = [band[2] for band in raster_data if typeof(band[2]) == Array{UInt16,2}]
data_matrix = hcat([vec(band) for band in band_data]...)
```

The second line extracts the raster band data, while the third line iteratively converts each raster band matrix into a vector, then concatenates the vectors together into a single matrix. The concatenated matrix can then be inputted into Clustering.jl `kmeans()`.

Julia

```
clusters = kmeans(data_matrix', k)
```

The ' after `data_matrix` transposes the matrix before passing it to `kmeans()`. `K` should be a numeric value equal to the number of intended clusters. The optimal number of clusters will need to be determined by the reader. This can be done with a variety of methods, such as a Davies-Bouldin Index or the Elbow Method. Readers should convert the output a matrix with the same dimensions as the input raster.

In Julia, this can be done with `reshape()`:

```
rows, cols = size(band_data[1])
clustered_raster = reshape(clusters.assignments, rows, cols)
```

Readers will then want to inspect the output raster to determine the cluster assignments that most closely align with their targeted features.

In Julia, this can be done with `Plots.jl heatmap()`:

using Plots

```
colormap = [:red, :green, :blue, :yellow, :purple]
heatmap(clusters, color=:auto, clim=(1, k), colorbar_title="Cluster ID", c=colormap)
```

In Julia, readers can then create a bit screen with their chosen assignments with:

```
screen = (clusters .== x)*
```

Note that x should equal the cluster assignment number for the identified cluster. Readers can screen for multiple clusters by adding an or operator “.” between conditions:

```
screen = (clusters .== x) .| (clusters .== y)
```

Readers can finally save their screen map to disk with ArchGDAL.jl ArchGDAL.write():

```
using ArchGDAL
screen = Int.(screen)*
ArchGDAL.write("clusters.tif", screen) do dataset
    ArchGDAL.createcopy(dataset, screen, driver="GTiff")
End
```

The bit (TRUE | FALSE) screen will first need to be converted to integer values with Int().

Step 10: Aggregate Cluster Results into Zonal Statistics and Save as a CSV (Other)

Once the cluster assignment screen has been saved to disk as a GeoTiff, readers should find a way to aggregate their land classification analysis into meaningful values. Depending on the individual use case, existing shapefiles, such as political boundaries, may or may not be available.

Assuming that readers have an existing shapefile that covers the extent of their selected MGRS tile, the extraction and aggregation process can be done with a variety of tools, such as GDAL and the R Raster library. The open-source exact extract command line utility is available at <https://github.com/isciences/exactextract> and through the R exactextract library. This step assumes that readers have followed the installation instructions for exactextract on the GitHub repository.

Assuming readers have a shapefile called “plantations.shp” and a saved cluster screen called “clusters.tif”, the process of creating zonal statistics with exactextract is as simple as opening a command line terminal and running:

```
exactextract -r “coverage:clusters.tif” -p plantations.shp -f plantations -s
“mean(coverage)” -o output.csv
```

If readers are working with longitudinal data, they can run exactextract over multiple cluster screens by adding additional tifs with -r

```
exactextract -r "coverage_2018:clusters_2018.tif" -r "coverage_2019:clusters_2019.tif" -r  
"coverage_2020:clusters_2020.tif" -p plantations.shp -f plantations -s  
"mean(coverage_2018)" -s "mean(coverage_2019)" -s "mean(coverage_2020)" -o  
output.csv
```

The resulting output, output.csv, can then be loaded in R, Stata, or another statistical application for analysis.